

Kingdom of Edom

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Levantine Religion, Canaanite Religions, Syro-Palestinian Religion

Edom appears to have had two major phases of activity during the Iron Age (1200–550 BCE). Early in the Iron Age activity and social complexity was focused in the lowland regions of the Arabah and centered in large part on the industrial exploitation of copper resources in the region. This period was marked by primarily mobile non-sedentary communities, and as such, lacks substantial textual or settlement data. This entry focusses on the second major phase of Edom, dated to the late Iron Age (ca. 750–550 BCE), where there is substantially more robust data. At this time Edom was centered in the highlands of southern Transjordan around a series of small settlements and agricultural villages, dominated by its foremost city of Busayra. The region yet retained a large mobile pastoral component. Substantial textual sources for this region are lacking, so much of the relevant data derives from short inscriptions and archaeological data. Similarities in lifeways, social structures, etc., between Edom and its neighbors to the north and west (Moab, Ammon, Judah), allows for relevant comparisons and extrapolations to be made, particularly concerning religious practices. Similar to the other Iron Age polities of the southern Levant, many gods are attested in Edom, though the deity Qos (Qaus/Qws) appears to have served as the foremost deity of the land, its populace, and of the ruling elite of Edom. Qos appears to have functioned as a local variant of the “storm god” and/or “divine warrior” type. Knowledge of Qos is primarily restricted to short inscriptions and names. Evidence for religious practices (to Qos and other deities) can be found in individual homes, at poorly understood regional ritual sites, at several shrines (Horvat Qitmit and En Hazeva) and in a large temple complex at Busayra that likely centered on the worship of Qos and presumably a consort.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 550 BCE

Region: Edom

Region tags: Israel, Jordan

The Iron Age Kingdom of Edom and its neighboring regions.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Danielson, Andrew. 2020. “On the History and Evolution of Qws: The Portrait of a First Millennium BCE Deity Explored through Community Identity.” *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 20/2: 112–188.
- Source 2: Dearman, Andrew. 1995. “Edomite Religion: A Survey and an Examination of Some Recent Contributions.” In *You Shall Not Abhor an Edomite for He Is Your Brother: Edom and Seir in History and Tradition*, edited by Diana Edelman, 119–36. Atlanta: Scholars Press.
- Source 3: Bartlett, John. 1989. *Edom and the Edomites*. Sheffield: Journal for the Study of the Old Testament.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://edomarchaeology.com/>

– Source 1 Description: International Conference on Edom, June 2021

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: N/A

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Israelite Religions, Arabian Religions, Transjordanian Religions

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Neutral contact in large (particularly for economic purposes), with alliances among other southern Levantine states, though this does not exclude violent episodes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: With the Babylonian Empire, and to a degree, ancient Israel and Judah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: A large Temple Complex on the acropolis of the capital city of Busayra demonstrates a close link between the palace and temple.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: At least with regards to the main temple complex in the capital city.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to estimate at population sizes, as not all settlement sites have been firmly identified, and the region would have housed a large mobile pastoralist component. On the basis of population estimates per settled hectare (Broshi and Finkelstein 1992), we could hypothesize that the region of Edom was inhabited by a population in the tens of thousands. See: Broshi, M., and I. Finkelstein. 1992. The Population of Palestine in Iron Age II. *BASOR* 287:47, 60.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most, if not all inhabitants of Edom would have recognized the god Qos (Qaus/Qws) as a central deity of the region and its inhabitants. Religious exclusivity was not a mandate, however, and within the polytheistic society, many other deities were recognized.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: Starting as one god among many within the region, the deity Qos becomes the most prominent deity of the region during the late Iron Age. Danielson, Andrew. 2020. "On the History and Evolution of Qws: The Portrait of a First Millennium BCE Deity Explored through Community Identity." *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 20/2: 112-188.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: The primary deity of this region, Qos, originates as one of many deities in the region before becoming the most prominent deity of the region. See discussion in Danielson (2020). Danielson, Andrew. 2020. "On the History and Evolution of Qws: The Portrait of a First Millennium BCE Deity Explored through Community Identity." *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 20/2: 112-188.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: At least no formal texts that have survived.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There is a large temple complex located on the acropolis of the capital city of Busayra (Bienkowski 2002:94-95; Porter 2004: 381-387) Bienkowski, Piotr. 2002. *Busayra: Excavations by Crystal-M. Bennett 1971-1980. British Academy Monographs in Archaeology* 13. Oxford: Oxford University. Porter, Benjamin. 2004. "Authority, Polity and Tenuous Elites in Iron Age Edom (Jordan)." *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 23 (4): 373-95.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 3375

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: Major cemeteries or tombs (apart from Wadi Fidan 40; see below) have not been excavated.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: Major cemeteries or tombs (apart from Wadi Fidan 40; see below) have not been excavated.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Yes. There are formal Temples, shrines and sacred spaces have been identified at Busayra (Bienkowski 2002:94-95), Horvat Qitmit (Beit-Arieh 1995), and En Hazeva (Cohen and Yisrael 1995, 1996). Additional and smaller-scale sacred spaces are certainly present, though they have not been formally and unambiguously identified (Danielson 2020: 126). Beit-Arieh, Itzhaq. 1995. Ḥorvat Qitmit: An Edomite Shrine in the Biblical Negev. Monograph Series 11. Tel Aviv: Institute of Archaeology of Tel Aviv University. Bienkowski, Piotr. 2002. Busayra: Excavations by Crystal-M. Bennett 1971-1980. British Academy Monographs in Archaeology 13. Oxford: Oxford University. Cohen, Rudolph, and Yigal Yisrael. 1995. "The Iron Age Fortresses at 'En Ḥaṣeva." *The Biblical Archaeologist* 58 (4): 223-35. Cohen, Rudolph, and Yigal Yisrael. 1996. "Smashing the Idols: Piecing Together an Edomite Shrine in Judah." *Biblical Archaeology Review* 22 (4): 40-51. Danielson, Andrew. 2020. "On the History and Evolution of Qws: The Portrait of a First Millennium BCE Deity Explored through Community Identity." *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 20/2: 112-188.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: See above discussion regarding Temples.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: For a more detailed discussion, consult the following resources: Beck, Pirhiya. 1995. "Catalogue of Cult Objects and Study of the Iconography." In *Horvat Qitmit: An Edomite Shrine in the Biblical Negev*, edited by Itzhaq Beit-Arieh, 27-197. Tel Aviv: Sonia and Marco Nadler Institute of Archaeology, Tel Aviv University. Beck, Pirhiya. 1996. "Horvat Qitmit Revisited via 'En Hazeva." *Tel Aviv* 23: 102-14.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Human headed Sphinx (Beck 1995: 152-153). Other zoomorphic elements are present, though it is unclear/unlikely that they are intended to be supernatural.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Mountains/hills and higher elevations especially.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Lack of sufficient evidence.

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely some type of underworld (Sheol) concept, but there is lack of sufficient evidence for a conclusive determination.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Evidence from Wadi Fidan 40 indicates that buried persons were covered with a shroud of animal skin and goat hair. Bodies were often flexed or semi-flexed in the graves. Within tomb contexts, the practice of secondary burial or deposition may be assumed.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Few mortuary contexts have been defined in Edom. The most robust data come from Wadi Fidan 40, dating primarily to the tenth century BCE, thus slightly predating our period of focus. The graves goods consist of: jewelry (semi-precious stones, copper alloy, iron, shell), seals, small figurines, and limited ceramic and wooden vessels. See further discussion in: Beherec, Marc, Mohammad Najjar, and Thomas Levy. 2014. "Wadi Fidan 40 and Mortuary Archaeology in the Edom Lowlands." In *New Insight into the Iron Age Archaeology of Edom, Southern Jordan*, edited by Thomas Levy, Mohammad Najjar, and Erez Ben-Yosef, 665–722. Los Angeles: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology. Beherec, Marc. 2011. "Nomads in Transition: Mortuary Archaeology in the Lowlands of Edom (Jordan)." Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, San Diego: University of California, San Diego. Levy, Thomas. 2008. "Ethnic Identity in Biblical Edom, Israel and Midian: Some Insights from Mortuary Contexts in the Lowlands of Edom." In *Exploring the Longue Duree: Essays in Honor of Lawrence E. Stager*, edited by J. David Schloen, 251–61. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other grave goods:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Few mortuary contexts have been defined in Edom. Wadi Fidan 40 consists of individual stone-lined cist graves with some evidencing stone paving and stone capstones, and frequently either aniconic or loosely anthropomorphic standing stones. The cists graves were designed to contain a single individual, usually, though not exclusively, in a flexed or semi-flexed position. Similarly, secondary burials were relatively common. The site of Ghraheh likely contains rock cut tombs, though these are poorly preserved. On the basis of parallels with Moab and Judah, we have every reason to suspect that rock cut and cave family tombs featuring secondary burial practices would have been common. Beherec, Marc, Mohammad Najjar, and Thomas Levy. 2014. "Wadi Fidan 40 and Mortuary Archaeology in the Edom Lowlands." In *New Insight into the Iron Age Archaeology of Edom, Southern Jordan*, edited by Thomas Levy, Mohammad Najjar, and Erez Ben-Yosef, 665-722. Los Angeles: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology. Bloch-Smith, Elizabeth. 1992. *Judahite Burial Practices and Beliefs about the Dead*. JSOT Supplement Series 123. Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press. Hart, Stephen. 1988. "Excavations at Ghraheh, 1986: Preliminary Report." *Levant* 20 (1): 89-99.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: See further discussion in: Beherec, Marc, Mohammad Najjar, and Thomas Levy. 2014. "Wadi Fidan 40 and Mortuary Archaeology in the Edom Lowlands." In *New Insight into the Iron Age Archaeology of Edom, Southern Jordan*, edited by Thomas Levy, Mohammad Najjar, and Erez Ben-Yosef, 665-722. Los Angeles: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology. Beherec, Marc. 2011. "Nomads in Transition: Mortuary Archaeology in the Lowlands of Edom (Jordan)." Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, San Diego: University of California, San Diego. Levy, Thomas. 2008. "Ethnic Identity in Biblical Edom, Israel and Midian: Some Insights from Mortuary Contexts in the Lowlands of Edom." In *Exploring the Longue Duree: Essays in Honor of Lawrence E. Stager*, edited by J. David Schloen, 251-61. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Several tombs that likely date to the late Iron Age (8th - 6th century) were identified at Ghreah, though they were heavily looted and little can be said regarding them. On the basis of regional parallels in the surrounding regions (Moab, Judah, etc.) we may confidently hypothesize that family tombs would have been a feature of the region. Hart, Stephen. 1988. "Excavations at Ghreah, 1986: Preliminary Report." *Levant* 20 (1): 89-99.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Within Edom, the god Qos (Qaus/Qws) is by far the most prominent. Other deities attested (primarily as theophoric elements in names) consist of: El, Shalem, Baal, and Ea. Iconography from the site of Horvat Qitmit is also strongly suggestive of Astarte or Asherah. There is no firm data for other spirits or divinized ancestors, though on the basis of comparisons to neighboring contexts additional spirits or revered ancestors are likely.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The most prominent deity Qos (Qaus/Qws) is likely a weather deity and or divine warrior. Danielson, Andrew. 2020. "On the History and Evolution of Qws: The Portrait of a First Millennium BCE Deity Explored through Community Identity." *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 20/2: 112-188.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data. Qos was not "physically" related to elites, though we may presume that would have acted on behalf of the deity claiming to be agents of the divine.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Qos was likely a weather deity and/or divine warrior. Potentially also, the Arabic etymology of his name suggests that he may be named after a divinized bow.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: Likely not. Qos (Qaus/Qws) was most likely a regional god, linked to this particular geographic space. Danielson, Andrew. 2020. "On the History and Evolution of Qws: The Portrait of a First Millennium BCE Deity Explored through Community Identity." *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 20/2: 112-188.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Likely in the sense of requiring sacrifices for appeasement.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: No entirely no, though some would have understood religious specialists as possessing this ability.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: No, though some monarchs may have claimed such an ability. Insufficient data.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: El, Shalem, Baal, Ea, and Asherah and/or Astarte are attested. Likely additional other semi-divine desert spirits and/or ancestors also, though data is insufficient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: At times, yes. Certain deities are associated with particular aspects of life (fertility, agriculture, disease, etc.)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Likely yes.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably in the sense of sacrifices provided for them.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Often the power of specific deities, or their role in religious ritual will be focusses within particular areas of life (e.g., fertility, childbirth).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is insufficient data, though messianic beliefs are unlikely.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Notes: Insufficient data, though very likely not. In surrounding, comparative regions castration was viewed positively.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– I don't know

Notes: Notes: Insufficient data, though at times it is likely.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Notes: Faunal data for sites in this region shows a preference for not consuming pig (*Sus scrofa*), though this preference was not necessarily linked to religious thought.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though very likely not.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data. The sacrifice of children is attested in extreme circumstances in neighboring regions, so it may have been present to a limited degree in Edom as well.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though votives or the sacrificing of property (animals) was a sign of continued reverence and favor-seeking to the gods.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Ritual practices at defined religious sites at Busayra, Horvat Qitmit, and En Hazeva, likely consisted of animal sacrifice, use of votive offerings, libations, and the burning of aromatics (together with the presumed associated chants/hymns etc.). The purpose of these rituals was likely to receive divine favor, make requests, and to "thank" the deity. Common requests and thanks would be associated with fertility (human, animal, and agriculture), well-being (health, prosperity), and protection (from enemies divine, human, or weather related).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data. Evidence suggests the burning of aromatics and at the least cannabis in surrounding regions. Arie, E., Rosen, B. and Namdar, D. 2020. "Cannabis and Frankincense at the Judahite Shrine of Arad." *Tel Aviv* 47: 5-28.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: Insufficient data, though references from the Hebrew Bible suggest that people in the region of Edom practiced circumcision (Jeremiah 9:25).

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Pig (*Sus scrofa*) was not consumed in significant quantities by persons in this region.

↳ Hair:

– I don't know

Notes: The iconography from the shrine at Horvat Qitmit suggests distinct styles of hair. How distinct this was from neighboring peoples is difficult to determine. Beck, Pirhiya. 1995. "Catalogue of Cult Objects and Study of the Iconography." In *Horvat Qitmit: An Edomite Shrine in the Biblical Negev*, edited by Itzhaq Beit-Arieh, 27-197. Tel Aviv: Sonia and Marco Nadler Institute of Archaeology, Tel Aviv University.

↳ Dress:

– I don't know

Notes: The iconography from the shrine at Horvat Qitmit suggests distinct styles of clothes. How distinct this was from neighboring peoples is difficult to determine. Beck, Pirhiya. 1995. "Catalogue of Cult Objects and Study of the Iconography." In *Horvat Qitmit: An Edomite Shrine in the Biblical Negev*, edited by Itzhaq Beit-Arieh, 27-197. Tel Aviv: Sonia and Marco Nadler Institute of Archaeology, Tel Aviv University.

↳ Ornaments:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Theophoric elements within names

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Fictive kinship terms were likely quite common within region, where social structures may be understood as segmentary lineage systems that employed fictive kinship terms to foster social alliances. Porter, Benjamin. 2004. "Authority, Polity and Tenuous Elites in Iron Age Edom (Jordan)." *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 23 (4): 373–95.

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data., though likely not. Welfare was most likely provided through kinship systems.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data., though likely not. Welfare was most likely provided through kinship systems.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data., though likely not. Welfare was most likely provided through kinship systems.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data., though likely not. Welfare was most likely provided through kinship systems.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: Insufficient data, though not education in a modern sense. Education in family craft/subsistence practices was most provided through kinship systems.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though likely not.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though protected roadways were likely controlled by the ruling (political) elite.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably by the state, though it is unknown the degree of a link between the political elite and the religious elite. It is quite possible that there was a degree of overlap. Evidence for "taxation" and/or redistribution systems is indicated by seals that identify state actors associated with standardized vessels (e.g., qws'nl jars). Divito, Robert. 1993. "The Tell el-Kheleifeh Inscriptions." In Nelson Glueck's 1938-1940 Excavations at Tell el-Kheleifeh: A Reappraisal, edited by Gary Pratico, 51-63. American Schools of Oriental Research Archaeological Reports. Atlanta, Georgia: Scholars Press.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though "judicial" rulings were likely meted out through kinship systems, or in extreme cases by the ruling elite.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s)

other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data, though persons and groups in Edom were likely conscripted by its kings in times of war.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Edom and its environs

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Literacy was not the norm. A small subset of persons were literate, functioning as scribes in the employ of elite persons for administrative, economic, or religious purposes.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Food was attained and provided for through kinship systems.

Bibliography

General References

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